

T-X Phase diagram of $(\text{NH}_4)_2\text{SO}_4/\text{H}_2\text{O}$

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Abstract : Using the mean field theory, we obtain the phase line equations for the liquid-solid I, liquid-solid II and solid I-solid II transitions in $(\text{NH}_4)_2\text{SO}_4/\text{H}_2\text{O}$. We fit our phase line equations to the experimental T-X phase diagram of this system. Thus, we are able to obtain the temperature and concentration dependencies of the order parameters and the free energies in this system.

Keywords : Phase diagram, ammonium sulfate, mean field theory.

$(\text{NH}_4)_2\text{SO}_4$ exhibits a phase transition from the paraelectric orthorhombic phase with the space group D_{2h}^{16} to the ferroelectric orthorhombic phase with the space group C_{2v}^9 (Refs. 1, 2). This ferroelectric phase involves ordering of two inequivalent $(\text{NH}_4)_I$ and $(\text{NH}_4)_{II}$ groups which are orientated antiparallel to one another. With these orientations of the tetrahedra, SO_4^{2-} is assigned as a pseudo-spin $\sigma = \pm 1$, which can be considered in an Ising model³. By defining two Ising variables as to specify the orientations of two kinds of ammonium ions and also by considering the coupling between pseudo-spins and phonon, an Ising model has been studied for ammonium sulphate⁴.

The mechanism of an order-disorder type of phase transition in $(\text{NH}_4)_2\text{SO}_4$ has been explained theoretically by means of the reorientation of the dipoles of the distorted NH_4^+ ions⁵. A soft mode model has also been suggested to explain the mechanism of the phase transition in $(\text{NH}_4)_2\text{SO}_4$ (Ref. 6).

Experimentally, there have been several studies using various techniques. Among those, NMR^{5,7-10}, neutron diffraction^{2,11}, ESR¹²⁻¹⁴, Raman¹⁵⁻¹⁷, IR^{15,18-20} and far-infrared²¹ spectroscopy, light scattering²², X-ray²³ and dielectric²⁴⁻²⁷ studies have been reported in the literature.

Ferroelectric and ferrielectric phase transitions in ammonium sulphate have also been modelled in the previous studies. A two sublattice model of ferroelectric phase transitions²⁸ has been introduced. Ferrielectric dielectric constant of $(\text{NH}_4)_2\text{SO}_4$ has been calculated and fitted to the experimental data²⁴. Recently, we have modelled ferrielectric dielectric behaviour of $(\text{NH}_4)_2\text{SO}_4$ by calculating the

temperature dependence of susceptibility using a mean field theory in this crystalline system²⁹.

As a binary mixture, the $(\text{NH}_4)_2\text{SO}_4/\text{H}_2\text{O}$ system has also been studied and, its equilibrium and metastability phase diagrams from 40 °C to –50 °C have been obtained³⁰. $(\text{NH}_4)_2\text{SO}_4/\text{H}_2\text{O}$ melts at –19.35 °C. Below –19.35 ± 0.05 °C, it undergoes a solid-solid (solid I-solid II) phase transition to form a tetrahydrate phase, as shown in T-X (ammonium sulphate wt %) phase diagram³⁰.

Table 1. Values of the coefficients which we obtained, when those equations indicated were fitted to the experimental data³⁰ for the liquid-solid I (L-I), liquid-solid II (L-II) and solid I-solid II (I-II) transitions in $(\text{NH}_4)_2\text{SO}_4/\text{H}_2\text{O}$. w denotes % weight of ammonium sulphate

L-I	Eq. (17)	L-II	Eq. (18)	I-II	Eq. (19)
a_1		b_1		c_1	
(°C/w)	–0.986	(°C/w)	10.043	(°C/w)	–2.024
a_2		b_2		c_2	
(°C/w ²)	–0.0204	(°C/w ²)	–0.136	(°C/w ²)	0.0364
a_3		b_3		c_3	
(°C/w ³)	$–1.96 \times 10^{-4}$	(°C/w ³)	0.040	(°C/w ³)	$–2.7 \times 10^{-1}$

In this study we obtain the phase line equations for the liquid-solid I-solid II phases in the temperature-composition (ammonium sulphate) phase diagram of $(\text{NH}_4)_2\text{SO}_4/\text{H}_2\text{O}$ system using a mean field theory. We fit our phase line equations to the experimental data for the $(\text{NH}_4)_2\text{SO}_4/\text{H}_2\text{O}$ system³⁰. By means of our calculated phase line equations for the T-X phase diagram of $(\text{NH}_4)_2\text{SO}_4/\text{H}_2\text{O}$, the critical

behaviour of some thermodynamic quantities can be predicted close to the transitions between liquid-solid I-solid II phases in this system.

In Section 2 we give an outline of our mean field model for the $(\text{NH}_4)_2\text{SO}_4/\text{H}_2\text{O}$ system. In Section 3 we give our calculations and results. Our brief discussion and conclusions are given in Section 4.

Theory :

In the mean field theory the free energies of the solid phases can be written in terms of the order parameters. Because of the symmetry reasons, the free energies will be expanded in the even powers of the order parameters. Hence, the free energies of the solid I and II phases of $(\text{NH}_4)_2\text{SO}_4$ are

$$F_I = \alpha_2 \mu^2 + \alpha_4 \mu^4 + \alpha_6 \mu^6 \quad (1)$$

and

$$F_{II} = \beta_2 v^2 + \beta_4 v^4 + \beta_6 v^6 \quad (2)$$

where μ and v are the order parameters of the solid I and II phases, respectively. Since, we study here a T-X phase diagram of the $(\text{NH}_4)_2\text{SO}_4/\text{H}_2\text{O}$ system, we assume that in eqs. (1) and (2) the parameters α_2, α_4 and α_6 ; β_2, β_4 and β_6 are all dependent upon the temperature and concentration. Due to the fact that the phase lines in the T-X phase diagram of this system represent a first order phase transition, we take $\alpha_2 > 0$, $\alpha_4 < 0$ and $\alpha_6 > 0$; $\beta_2 > 0$, $\beta_4 < 0$ and $\beta_6 > 0$. On the other hand, the free energy of the liquid phase can be taken as

$$F_L = 0 \quad (3)$$

Thus, the phase line equations for the liquid-solid I, liquid-solid II and solid I-solid II are given by $F_I = 0$, $F_{II} = 0$ and $F_I = F_{II}$ respectively.

In order to apply the condition for the first order transition between liquid and solid I phases, we minimize the free energy F_I with respect to the order parameter μ , which gives

$$\mu^2 = \frac{1}{3\alpha_6} [-\alpha_4 + (\alpha_4^2 - 3\alpha_2\alpha_6)^{1/2}] \quad (4)$$

Using μ^2 (eq. (4)) in F_I (eq. (1)) together with eq. (3), one gets

$$\alpha_4^2 = 4\alpha_2\alpha_6 \quad (5)$$

or

$$a = \alpha_4^2 - 4\alpha_2\alpha_6 = 0 \quad (6)$$

This is the phase line equation for the liquid-solid I transition, which represents the melting curve in the phase diagram of $(\text{NH}_4)_2\text{SO}_4/\text{H}_2\text{O}$.

Similarly, the phase line equation for the melting curve

between liquid and solid II phases, can be obtained from the free energy F_{II} (eq. (2)) By minimizing F_{II} with respect to the order parameter v , we obtain the expression for v in terms of the coefficients β_2, β_4 and β_6 as follows :

$$v^2 = \frac{1}{3\beta_6} [-\beta_4 + (\beta_4^2 - 3\beta_2\beta_6)^{1/2}] \quad (7)$$

Also, by substituting eq. (7) into eq. (2), we get

$$b = \beta_4^2 - 4\beta_2\beta_6 = 0 \quad (8)$$

as the phase line equation for the liquid-solid II transition in $(\text{NH}_4)_2\text{SO}_4/\text{H}_2\text{O}$.

In order to derive the phase line equation for the transition between two solid phases, namely, solid I and solid II, we use the first condition that

$$c = F_I - F_{II} = 0 \quad (9)$$

for the first order transition, as indicated above. This can be established first by writing the order parameter μ of solid I phase using eq. (6) in the form

$$\mu^2 = \frac{1}{3\alpha_6} [-\alpha_4 + \frac{1}{2}(\alpha_4^2 + 3a)^{1/2}] \quad (10)$$

Similarly, the order parameter v of solid II phase can be written using eq. (8) as

$$v^2 = \frac{1}{3\beta_6} [-\beta_4 + \frac{1}{2}(\beta_4^2 + 3b)^{1/2}] \quad (11)$$

By substituting eq. (10) into eq. (1), the free energy of solid I will then become

$$F_I = \frac{d}{\alpha_6^2} \quad (12)$$

where

$$d = \frac{1}{108} [\alpha_4 + (9a - \alpha_4^2) - (\alpha_4^2 + 3a)^{3/2}] \quad (13)$$

Similarly, by substituting eq. (11) into eq. (2), the free energy of solid II can be expressed as

$$F_{II} = \frac{e}{\beta_6^2} \quad (14)$$

where

$$e = \frac{1}{108} [\beta_4 + (9b - \beta_4^2) - (\beta_4^2 + 3b)^{3/2}] \quad (15)$$

By obtaining the difference between F_I and F_{II} according to eq. (9), we get

$$c = \frac{d}{\alpha_6^2} - \frac{e}{\beta_6^2} = 0 \quad (16)$$

This represents the phase line equation for the transition between solid I and solid II in $(\text{NH}_4)_2\text{SO}_4/\text{H}_2\text{O}$.

Calculations and results :

In order to obtain T-X phase diagram of $(\text{NH}_4)_2\text{SO}_4/\text{H}_2\text{O}$, we used here our phase line equations, namely, eqs. (6), (8) and (16) for the liquid-solid I, liquid-solid II and solid I-solid II, respectively. They were expressed as functional forms of both temperature and concentration in the following :

$$a = 0 = (T - T_m) - [a_1(X - X_m) + a_2(X - X_m)^2 + a_3(X - X_m)^3] \quad (17)$$

for the liquid-solid I transition,

$$b = 0 = (T - T_m) - [b_1(X - X_m) + b_2(X - X_m)^2 + b_3(X - X_m)^3] \quad (18)$$

for the liquid-solid II transition, and

$$c = 0 = (T - T_m) - [c_1(X - X_m) + c_2(X - X_m)^2 + c_3(X - X_m)^3] \quad (19)$$

for the solid I-solid II transition in $(\text{NH}_4)_2\text{SO}_4/\text{H}_2\text{O}$. In eqs. (17-19), (T_m, X_m) denote the coordinates of the melting point. From the experimental T-X phase diagram of $(\text{NH}_4)_2\text{SO}_4/\text{H}_2\text{O}$, the melting point is located at $T_m = -19.515^\circ\text{C}$ and $X_m = 39.950$ as the weight percent of the ammonium sulphate³⁰. Eqs. (17-19) were then fitted to the experimental data for the T-X phase diagram of $(\text{NH}_4)_2\text{SO}_4/\text{H}_2\text{O}$ ³⁰ and the values of the best-fitted parameters were obtained. Along the melting curves of liquid-solid I and liquid-solid II, from fitting of eqs. (17) and (18), values of the parameters a_1, a_2 and a_3 (eq. (17)), b_1, b_2 and b_3 (eq. (18)) which we obtained, are tabulated in Table 1. Also, along the transition line between the solid phases, from fitting of eq. (19) values of the parameters c_1, c_2

and c_3 which we obtained, are given in Table 1. In Fig. 1 we plot the melting curves of liquid-solid I (eq. (17)) and liquid-solid II (eq. (18)) with the transition line between solid I and solid II (eq. (19)), which coincide at the melting point in $(\text{NH}_4)_2\text{SO}_4/\text{H}_2\text{O}$. The observed T-X data is also given in Fig. 1.

Discussion and conclusions :

We obtained in this study T-X phase diagram of $(\text{NH}_4)_2\text{SO}_4/\text{H}_2\text{O}$ by expanding the free energies of solid I and solid II phases in terms of their order parameters. Its phase diagram was obtained by deriving the phase line equations for the melting curves of solid I and solid II phases, and for the transition between those two solid phases in this system. By considering both the temperature and concentration dependencies of the coefficients α_2, α_4 and α_6 (eq. (1)), β_2, β_4 and β_6 (eq. (2)) in the expansion of the free energies, phase diagram which we calculated, was coincided with the experimental T-X phase diagram of $(\text{NH}_4)_2\text{SO}_4/\text{H}_2\text{O}$. As noted in the previous work, the experimental T-X phase diagram³⁰ contains data obtained from past bulk experiments³¹, which are essentially single-particle experiments to generate thermodynamic phase diagrams. The published data³¹ is well characterized with the experimental T-X phase diagram, as indicated previously³⁰. From the point of view of a calculated phase diagram, we conclude here that our calculated phase diagram based on the mean field theory is in accordance with the experimental T-X phase diagram, as shown in Fig. 1.

As mentioned earlier, the temperature and concentration dependencies of the coefficients, namely, α_2, α_4 and $\alpha_6; \beta_2, \beta_4$ and β_6 can lead us to predict some other thermodynamic quantities. Using these coefficients, as we predicted here the temperature and concentration dependencies of the order parameters (eqs. (10) and (11)) and the free energies (eqs. (12) and (14)), we can also predict those dependencies of the thermodynamic quantities such as the specific heat, thermal expansivity and isothermal compressibility within our mean field model studied here. Our predicted quantities can then be compared with the experimentally measured data.

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Fig. 1. Our calculated phase diagram of $(\text{NH}_4)_2\text{SO}_4/\text{H}_2\text{O}$. Calculated phase lines are represented by solid lines. Experimental data³⁰ are also here.

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